

KNOWLEDGE OF NURSING STUDENTS ABOUT PREMENSTRUAL SYNDROME PREVENTION AND HANDLING

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Abstract

Premenstrual syndrome is one of the health disorders that are difficult to identify accurately, this disorder is often experienced by women, especially in adolescence. Various physical, psychological and emotional symptoms, which are related to hormonal changes due to the menstrual cycle, have an impact on quality of life, the highest activity disorders occur at home then in society, school and finally in the office. Female students who experience disorders in their activities can have difficulty concentrating, not attending lectures, disorders in doing homework or college assignments. The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between the knowledge of female nursing students about how to prevent and treat premenstrual syndrome. This study uses an analytical observational research design with a cross-sectional research design. The research instrument uses a questionnaire and then the data obtained are analyzed using the Chi Square data analysis technique ($p < 0.05$). The research sample is a student of the S1 Nursing Study Program Level 2 STIKES Bhakti Husada Mulia Madiun who was selected using probability sampling. The independent variable is knowledge, while the dependent variable is prevention and handling of Premenstrual syndrome. The research instrument is an online-based questionnaire. The results of data analysis showed a p value of 0.043 (< 0.05) indicating that there is a relationship between knowledge of premenstrual syndrome and prevention and treatment in 2nd year female students of STIKES Bhakti Husada Mulia Madiun.

Keywords: Pre menstruation; knowledge; female teenager.

1. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a transition period from childhood to adulthood, so there will be a lot of rapid growth and development both physically and mentally [1]. A woman normally experiences menstruation or menstruation when she enters adolescence or early adulthood, this becomes a cycle in a woman's life journey. Menstruation or menstruation is a time when the uterine wall of a woman falls off, blood is released through the vagina, and occurs periodically. This occurs because there is no fertilization of a woman's mature egg. Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) is a discomfort or physical and mental symptoms that arise when women are about to experience their menstrual cycle. Premenstrual Syndrome is a collection of symptoms that include physical, emotional, cognitive, and behavioral changes [2]. These symptoms usually appear ten to fourteen days before menstruation and disappear when menstruation begins, which makes it very difficult to carry out daily activities. Premenstrual syndrome is quite common, occurring in about 70 to 90% of women of

reproductive age. Premenstrual symptoms are more common in women aged 20 to 40 years, and can interfere with various aspects of their lives. It can disappear after bleeding, but can persist afterward. Premenstrual syndrome (PMS) has a high morbidity rate. Although premenstrual syndrome is not life-threatening, it can affect women's productivity and mentality. About 75% of women complain of premenstrual syndrome symptoms and 30% of them require treatment [3]. In the young age group, premenstrual syndrome is very common, indicating that there is a very significant health problem. The incidence of premenstrual syndrome is reported to occur in 20-30% of premenopausal women and 30-40% during reproductive age women [4].

Based on research conducted in Indonesia through Youth-Friendly Health Services (PKRR) in 2020, 90% of women of reproductive age experienced PMS symptoms. Menstrual disorders in Indonesia in 2020 were 38.45%. However, in 2019 the prevalence of PMS reached 58.1%. The prevalence of premenstrual syndrome (PMS) in Indonesia is increasing and around 80% of adolescent women experience premenstrual syndrome symptoms that can interfere with daily life [5]. Premenstrual syndrome is a complaint that usually begins one week to several days before menstruation, and disappears after menstruation comes, although sometimes it continues until menstruation stops adapting and regulating both internal and external pressures (stressors). In most of their menstrual cycles, most women of reproductive age usually experience one or more premenstrual symptoms. Each cycle can experience different symptoms in intensity and frequency. Emotional and behavioral irritability, depression, anxiety, fatigue, decreased concentration, swelling and discomfort in the breasts and pain in the abdominal area are the most severe and most common effects of premenstrual syndrome. If premenstrual syndrome is left untreated, it will cause more severe disorders or what is often called Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder (PMDD) [6]. Decreased productivity of PMS sufferers related to complaints such as difficulty concentrating, becoming forgetful, decreased enthusiasm, irritability, and emotional lability, as well as decreased coordination abilities.

This study was conducted on 2nd year students majoring in nursing, this allows the results of the study to see whether there is a relationship between knowledge and preventive actions and their handling of STDs felt by students. 2nd year students were chosen because in general at this 2nd year students have received basic knowledge about health, especially about reproductive health.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative method with an analytical observational research design [7]. The research sample was 138 nursing students taking semester 2. Sample selection was based on probability sampling, then the results were analyzed using the Chi Square data analysis technique ($p < 0.05$). The study was conducted while students were actively studying at the Stikes Bhakti Husada Mulia Madiun campus.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Result

General Data

Table 1: Age Range of Respondent.

Age	Frequency	%
19 - 20 tahun	87	63.0
21 - 22 tahun	49	35.5
23 - 24 tahun	2	1.4
Total	138	100.0

Source: Primary data (2024)

The average age of the 2nd semester students is based on the regular class and employee class, so there is a fairly large age gap between them. However, it can be seen that the most age is 19-20 years, namely 87 respondents (63.0%), this data shows that most of the respondents who took part in this study were gen z.

3.2 Specific Data

Table 2: Case Processing Summary

	Frequency		%		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Usia * TOTAL_K	138	100.0	0	0.0	138	100.0

Source: Primary data (2024)

Table 2: Case Processing Summary

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.301 ^a	2	.043
Likelihood Ratio	7.097	2	.029
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.976	1	.160
N of Valid Cases	138		

Source: Primary data (2024)

The results of data processing show that the Chi Square value is 0.043 or <0.05 so it can be said that there is an influence between student knowledge and handling of premenstrual syndrome.

4. Discussion

4.1 Characteristic Data Respondent

Table 1 explains that the number of respondents aged 19-20 years is 87 respondents (63%), respondents aged 21-22 years are 49 respondents (35.5%), while respondents aged 23-24 years are 2 respondents (1.4%). The total number of respondents is 183 respondents taken by probability, so it is possible that there are still students who have not become respondents at the time the research was conducted. Health education is a process to increase knowledge and awareness of a health condition in order to better understand one's own condition [8]. In health students, basic health education has been taught, making it possible to apply it to everyday life behaviour.

4.2 Premenstrual Syndrome

Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) or also called premenstrual tension, around 80-90% of women experience PMS [8]. The symptoms of PMS that often appear are swollen breasts, sore nipples, irritability, stomach cramps, fatigue, headaches, bloating, constipation, and acne. A woman is said to have PMS if she feels one of the physical symptoms and emotional symptoms. Some factors that are known to cause PMS are hormonal imbalance, lifestyle and stress or life pressures. Poor lifestyle factors, such as lack of exercise, lack of sleep, and weight gain are known to worsen PMS [9].

Knowledge about premenstrual syndrome (PMS) is an important aspect for teenagers, they must pay attention to the conditions they experience, such as premenstrual syndrome (PMS) as an anticipation of preventing other more severe symptoms, not letting it be and normalizing [10]. If PMS is left untreated, there will be impacts felt by the teenager, including decreased concentration in learning and decreased activity when PMS occurs [10]. Most teenagers who experience premenstrual syndrome (PMS) will experience both physical and psychological disorders in their daily lives, this is also a concern for midwives to promote health to young women [6].

Previous research by Masta Hutasoit (2022) which discussed PMS in adolescents had the result that health education can have a good influence on adolescent girls, especially those experiencing PMS [8]. These results show similarities with the results of this study, namely that there is a relationship between knowledge and handling of PMS in adolescents, namely students. This result is also reinforced by the results of the Chi Square test which shows a value of 0.043 which means that there is a relationship between knowledge and prevention and handling carried out by respondents.

4.3 Knowledge of Nursing Students About Premenstrual Syndrome

Knowledge is the output of information obtained by students during lectures. Students majoring in health have obtained basic health knowledge that is useful in everyday life. This is certainly an added value for students because they can use this knowledge for prevention efforts if abnormal things are found in the body's condition. PMS has a bad impact on a woman's condition, especially if the condition is quite severe experienced by teenagers while doing daily activities such as college, this causes a decrease in the quality of the person and affects their social life [11]. The positive impact of lectures in the health field is to provide knowledge about self-care if things are experienced such as PMS. As a result, by reducing this impact, PMS will feel lighter and can minimize its condition. The knowledge of Stikes Bhakti Husada Mulia students on PMS is quite good so that the relationship between knowledge and how to handle PMS can be realized well, even though the respondents are still at Level 2. So as not to normalize the symptoms felt, students will take action to see a doctor if they feel abnormal symptoms.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The results of data analysis showed a p value of 0.043 (<0.05) indicating that there is a relationship between knowledge of premenstrual syndrome and prevention and treatment in 2nd year female students of STIKES Bhakti Husada Mulia Madiun.

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